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Hydrocarbons Alcohols and Phytosterols from the Leaves of *Daucus carota*, Nantes**

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LEAVES (900 gm) of *Daucus carota*, Nantes (Umbelleferae) (commonly known as Pahari Gajar) collected from the surroundings of Aligarh district were air-dried, powdered and extracted with hot light petroleum (60-80°). A total of 18.6 gm. (2.06%) extract was obtained, which was subjected to chromatographic separation over neutral activated alumina (30 fold excess).

Elution with light petroleum (60-80°) yielded a colourless waxy product (300 mg), m. p. 57-58° (acetone), TLC-homogeneous (Silica gel-2% AgNO₃). I.R. spectrum indicated the presence of *n*-alkanes with a long chain. This fraction was then analysed by gas liquid chromatography which represented the homologous series of *n*-alkanes C₁₅-C₃₉ with maximum occurrence of C₂₉ (19.8%), C₂₇ (14.3%), C₃₁ (12.6%) and C₃₃ (10.0%) (Table 1). Odd carbon *n*-alkanes

prevailed in higher members only of the series whereas the quantitative preponderance of odd-carbon *n*-alkanes in the lower ones was not so significant¹. Some other hydrocarbons (mono methyl branched) were also present in small amounts².

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF *n*-ALKANES AND FREE ALCOHOLS[†]

No. of C-atoms	<i>n</i> -alkanes %	free alcohols %
15-21	traces	—
22	0.5	1.2
23	0.6	0.3
24	1.4	10.4
25	3.0	1.3
26	4.8	34.8
27	14.3	2.4
28	9.1	41.0
29	19.8	1.6
30	7.4	5.2
31	12.6	—
32	6.1	—
33	10.0	—
34	3.0	—
35	2.3	—
36	0.5	—
37 38,39	traces-	—

[†]According to GLC analysis.

Further elution with light petroleum : benzene (1:1) gave a mixture of alcohols (275 mg). This fraction on GLC analysis exhibited a homologous series of primary alcohols (C₂₃-C₃₀) with maximum occurrence of C₂₈ (4.6%), C₂₆ (34.8%) and C₂₄ (10.4%) (Table 1). Even alcohols prevailed as usual^{3,4}. From this mixture only *n*-hexacosanol, m.p. 77-78° (Lit⁵, m.p. 79.5°) could be crystallised from methanol (TLC-homogeneous). It was characterised by preparation of its acetate⁶ (m.p. 64-65°) and by direct comparison with authentic specimen (m.m.p., co-TLC).

Elution with benzene gave the sterol fraction which on crystallisation from methanol gave shining crystals (200 mg), m.p. 137-40°, TLC-homogeneous (Silica gel-5% AgNO₃, several solvent systems). Spectral data indicated it to be a mixture of sterols which could be separated and identified by combined GC-MS. The trimethylsilyl ethers were found to contain mainly two components with two other minor constituents and were identified by direct comparison of GLC retention

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TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF PHYTOSTEROLS

Compound	RRT	Molecular ion	% of sterols	Identity
1	1.00	458	3 27C 5	Cholesterol
2	1.29	472	5 28C 5	Campesterol*
3	1.36	484	45 29C 5,22	Stigmasterol*
4	1.59	486	47 29C 5	β -sitosterol*

*(or C₂₄ epimer as neither GLC nor MS can distinguish between C₂₄ epimers).

times and mass spectra^{7,8} with those of authentic specimens run under identical GC-MS conditions. The results are summarised in Table 2.

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